

Assessment of Natural Background Radiation Exposure in the Federal Capital Territory of Nigeria

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Abstract:

The detrimental effects of environmental contamination and deterioration on health are a worldwide concern and Nigerian environmental and public authorities continue to be concerned about the risk to public health. The water, the sky, construction materials and the earth's crust all release natural background radiation that contaminates the environment around us. Additionally, people are exposed to background radiation that comes from internal, cosmic, and terrestrial sources, although, the altitude determines the amount of cosmic radiation exposure, and high altitudes result in large radiation doses. Monitoring the amounts of

radiation to which humans are exposed, either directly or indirectly, requires an understanding of the natural background radiation in the environment. The current study attempted to create a baseline of outdoor background radiation in FCT for exposure rate, absorbed dose rate, annual effective dose equivalent, and excess life cancer risk. The study used a very sensitive survey meter to measure the BIR. The average BIR value found in the research areas is marginally below the 0.013mRh⁻¹ global BIR level, indicating an almost high BIR level for the FCT while the absorbed dose rates of 105.85nGy/hr was greater than the 59nGy/hr global population weighted average gamma dose rates estimate. The obtained annual effective dosage equivalent value is greater than the global average normal annual effective dosage level for outdoor environments, and the excess lifetime cancer risk values were higher than the 0.29×10⁻³ allowable level as reported by UNSCEAR & ICRP. Therefore, the general people and those who live in environmentally sensitive areas may experience immediate health effects from contamination and radiation levels at the current rates.

Keywords: BIR, Radiation, Dose rate, FCT, Nigeria.

Introduction

The detrimental effects of environmental contamination and deterioration on health are a worldwide concern. Background ionization radiation can be said to be one type of

environmental contamination that should be taken into account, particularly when it surpasses safe public and occupational levels. The International Atomic Energy Agency (2007) defined background radiation as the dose or dose rate (or an observed measure related to the

dose or dose rate) due to all sources other than the one or sources mentioned. Hence, a distinction is made between the dose resulting from a purposefully inserted and designated source and the dose that is already present in an area, which is termed here as "background". This is crucial because radiation measurements of a given radiation source may be impacted by the surrounding background. For example, measuring radioactive contamination in a backdrop of gamma radiation may result in a total reading that is higher than what would be predicted from the contamination alone. The total radiation dose measurement at a location, however, is typically referred to as background radiation if no radiation source is identified as being of concern. This is typically the case when an ambient dose rate is measured for environmental reasons, as is the case in the current study. Such background ionizing radiations are freely and naturally occurring within the surrounding or encompassing environment, and they are constantly exposed to the population or tenements and other living things in such area.

Due to the rise in human activity, this exposure, like that in other locations, has increased over time. As a result, there is significant concern due to the potential harm that greater levels of this exposure may cause (Ugbede, 2018). Cosmic rays that reach Earth from space and naturally occurring radioactive materials are two common sources of natural radiation (Ugbede, 2018) and the non-series ^{40}K and the series ^{238}U and ^{232}Th , along with their decay or associated products, are the most significant of these minerals. Over time, human activity, particularly in industrial settings, has led to a rise in background ionizing radiation in the environment which were originally caused by natural sources of terrestrial primordial radionuclide and interplanetary cosmic rays (Abdulmalik et al., 2015). This is due to the fact that raw materials utilized in homes, schools, and businesses include naturally occurring radioactive materials (NORM), which, after going through certain industrial processes, are subsequently released into the environment as waste. Therefore, makes background radiation

to be found in all parts of the environment, including foods, rocks, soil, water, sediments, and even the human body (UNSCEAR, 2010). Though, depending on the geology and topography of a particular area, radioactive nuclides concentrations and gamma radiation might differ greatly (Ugbede, 2018).

Moreover, additional sources that have added to the rise in background radiation exposure and doses include the use of radiation sources in nuclear power plants, research facilities, fertilizer manufacturing, medical diagnosis and therapy, consumer products, and nuclear weapon. These make exposure to this elevated radiation levels and dosages in the environment to pose a significant risk to human health and the ecosystem. This is because Ionizing radiations are extremely powerful particles that have a strong ability to penetrate materials and according to Melue and Eke (2020), this type of radiation excites and ionizes biological cells, changing their structural makeup. These high doses of gamma radiation can have a variety of negative consequences on humans, including mutation and all types of cancer as well as other disorders or diseases (Ugbede, 2018). Children and adolescents are more vulnerable to the harmful effects of radiation than older adults are, making them more vulnerable to these consequences (Kamiya and Sasatani 2012). Oxford Academic (2020) conducted epidemiological studies on a number of populations, including children (Pediatric CT) exposed to radiation, such as survivors of atomic bombs or patients undergoing radiotherapy. The results indicated a significant increase in cancer risk at doses exceeding 100 mSv, and Kamiya and Sasatani (2012) suggested that the risk may increase even at lower doses (between 50 and 100 mSv). It has been determined that the amount of radiation that damages tissue and/or organs is dependent upon the radiation dose that is absorbed. The type of radiation and the sensitivity of the body's various tissues and organs both affect the potential harm from an absorbed dose.

According to Weisstein (2014), radiation is a type of energy emission or transmission that travels across space or a material medium as waves or

particles. In this scenario, atoms emit energy in the form of electromagnetic waves or particles from both the surface and the subsurface. This energy is referred to as ionizing radiation. Individuals are exposed to infrared radiation (IR) from both artificial and natural sources, including plants, water, and subterranean mineral deposits. Artificial sources include j-rays and medical gadgets. In research, industry, agriculture, medicine, and other fields, infrared radiation has numerous advantageous applications. However, when IR is used more often, there is also a greater chance that it could pose health risks if not controlled or regulated. When radiation doses surpass specific thresholds, acute health problems like skin burns or acute radiation syndrome can happen. Even at modest doses, radiation can raise the chance of longer-term impacts like cancer. Therefore, it is crucial to assess the health risk associated with background radiation, which is defined as the amount of ionizing radiation in the environment at a certain location that is not caused by the intentional introduction of radiation sources (Tsepav et al., 2018). One of the unavoidable features of human existence is exposure to background ionizing radiation from natural sources and this makes measuring background ionizing gamma radiation to be crucial for the health of communities since it is the most common form of ionizing radiation exposure (Ali and colleagues, 2014)

The need to look into background ionization radiation levels and doses in communities or area councils of the Federal capital territory was suggested by the apparent implications of increased background radiation levels in the environment as a result of exposure to the ground surface and other sources. The goal of this research is therefore to provide baseline information on ambient background radiation. In order to assess how the background radiations from different radiation sources impact the tenement and other living things in the research locations, it will also assess the environmental quality of the targeted places.

Materials and Methods

The Study Area

This study is carried out in all the area councils in Nigeria's Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja. FCT is located at coordinates of 9.05790N and 7.49510E. It is bordered or surrounded by the states of Niger to the west and northwest, Kaduna to the northeast, Nassarawa to the east and south, and Kogi to the southwest. Its population, according to census data from 2006, is 776,298 and its total area is 7,315 km². The Federal Capital Territory is comparatively temperate, much like certain northern states of Nigeria. January through April is often the hottest month in the FCT. March is the hottest month, with an average daily maximum temperature of over 30°C, or 86°F, in the city. The territory experiences a wet season from April to October annually, with December being the coolest month of the harmattan season. A windy and foggy atmosphere coexist with high relative humidity during the harmattan.

Crystalline rocks made of gneisses and granites underlie the area. Savanna dominates the vegetation, with a little amount of woodland. Produced by agriculture, the backbone of the economy, are beans, yams, millet, corn (maize), and sorghum. The ethnic groups that make up the population are mostly dairy farmers and include the Gwari, Koro, Ganagana, Gwandara, Afo, and Bassa. There are also Fulani and Hausa people living there and clay, tin, feldspar, gold, iron ore, lead, marble, and talc are examples of mineral resources found in FCT. FCT, which consists of six local government units or area councils, has one senatorial district. The Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC), Kuje (KJ), Bwari (BW), Kwali (KW), Abaji (AB), and Gwagwalada (GW) are the area councils with their acronyms as used in this study.

Field Procedure and Calculations

An S.E International, Inc. (USA) portable radiation alert Ranger with serial number of R313227 which is a nuclear radiation monitor meter was used to measure the Background Ionizing Radiation (BIR) levels in the area

councils. The equipment underwent pre-operational, functionality, and quality inspections before the monitoring exercise so as to guarantee that it was in flawless, precise, and working order before the radiation measurements. After each survey data point was located, measurements of background radiation were made by scanning the area through 3600. A Geiger Muller tube in the detector can identify α , β , γ , and x-rays. The Geiger tube produces an electrical pulse when radiation enters it and the CPU counts this pulse and displays the result on the screen in CPM, mR/h, or $\mu\text{Sv/h}$ units. Each area council has five data points where measurements were made. Nonetheless, five readings were obtained within each data point at intervals of one meter from the center, for a total of twenty-five reading points per area council. With the use of a GIS tool, the locations were carefully chosen to evenly cover the study region or area. The coordinates for each of the five reading zones for each data point, in addition to the original data points, were created using the GIS application. The monitor was positioned at a level, open surface one meter above the ground (Olarinoye et al., 2010). A Geographical Positioning System (GPS) was used to pinpoint the exact positions of every data point inside the research areas. The National Council on Radiation Protection and Measurements (1993) recommended that readings be obtained between 1200 and 1700 hours because this is when the radiation meter responds to radiation the highest and as such was adhered to in this study. To enable sample points to retain their original environmental characteristics, an in-situ approach to measurement was used, following standard procedure of raising the detector tube 1.0 m above ground level with its window facing the point under investigation (Agbalagba et al, 2016; Ugbede and Echeweozo, 2017).

Using SPSS version 24, twenty-five measurements of the dosage rate in $\mu\text{Sv/hr}$ were taken from each data point to generate an average dose rate per data point (this value is what is reported in this report). The researchers were able to view the measured data on the display screen of the Ranger Multi-survey meter. The average exposure rates in $\mu\text{Sv/hr}$ were

converted to equivalent dose (ED) rates in mSv/yr using UNSCEAR (2008) guidelines. Using the mean BIR exposure rate from each data point, a number of Radiological Health Indices calculations were performed, such as Absorbed Dose Rate (ADR), Annual Effective Dose Equivalent (AEDE), and Excess Lifetime Cancer Risk (ELCR), using equations below (Rafique et al., 2014 and Agbalagba, 2017), to quantitatively assess the environmental quality and determine any potential effects of radiation on the tenements within the immediate environments.

Formula of Health Hazard Indices Used in this Study

To provide a more accurate and trustworthy assessment of the health condition of an individual exposed to radiation, various known radiation health hazard indices analysis is used in radiation research (Diab et al., 2008; Kabir et al., 2009; Zarie and Al Mugren, 2010; Senthilkumar, 2010). The following radiation hazard indices were used, among others, to evaluate the radiation hazards related to the gamma radiation of all the FCT area councils: absorbed dose rate, equivalent dose, annual equivalent dose rate, excess life cancer risk, and effective dose to various organs.

Occupancy and Conversion Factor

The percentage of an individual's overall exposure duration to a radiation is known as the occupancy factor (NCRP, 1993). There were eight thousand seven hundred and sixty hours used annually, or 8760 hours. The suggested indoor and outdoor occupancy factors by UNSCEAR (1988) were 0.8 and 0.2, respectively. Using the relation, the nuclear radiation meter's count rate per minute (CPM) reading was converted to milli-roentgen per hour (mRh-1).

$$\text{Count rate per minute (CMP)} = 10^{-3} \text{ roentgen} \times \frac{\text{Q.F}}{(1)}$$

where Q.F., or the quality factor, is one for the external environment.

Absorbed Dose Rate

The absorbed dose is the amount that most accurately captures the effects of radiation on humans, upon which all other radiation protection-related variables are dependent on it. It is employed to evaluate the possibility of any biochemical alterations in particular tissues. It measures the amount of radiation energy that a person who could be exposed to it might absorb (Agbalagba, 2016). Using the conversion factor, the data acquired for the external exposure rate in $\mu\text{R/h}$ was likewise transformed into the absorbed dosage rate.

$$1_{\mu\text{R/hr}} = 8.7 \frac{\text{nGy}}{\text{hr}} = \frac{8.7 \times 10^{-3}}{1/8760} \mu\text{Gy}^{-1} = 76.212 \mu\text{Gy}^{-1} \quad (2)$$

Exposure or Equivalent Dose Rate (Outdoor)

The amount of radiation in the vicinity or an area is known as the exposure, and the amount that is anticipated to be absorbed by the individual is known as the dose. We apply the National Council on Radiation Protection and Measurement guidance (Avwiriet al., 2013) to calculate the whole body equivalent dose rate during a one-year period:

$$1\text{mR/hr} = \frac{0.96 \times 24 \times 365}{100} \text{mSv/yr} \quad (3)$$

Annual Effective Dose Equivalent (AEDE)

According to ICRP (1990) the term "effective dose" refers to the radiation dose parameter that accounts for the absorbed dose that each exposed organ receives as well as the organs' relative sensitivity. This protection level Dosimetry quantity has the potential to serve as a rough gauge for stochastic effect. The annual effective dose equivalent (AEDE) received by study area residents was determined using the computed absorbed dose rates. We utilized the UNSCEAR-recommended dose conversion ratio of 0.7Sv/Gy for the conversion coefficient from

absorbed dose in air to effective dose received by adults and an occupancy factor of 0.2 for outdoor exposure for calculating the AEDE (UNSCEAR, 1993). The annual effective dose equivalent is determined using the equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{AEDE (Outdoor)} (\text{mSv}^{-1}) &= \text{Absorbed dose} \\ &(\eta\text{Gy}^{-1}) \times 8760 \text{ h} \times 0.7\text{Sv/Gy} \times 0.2 \\ &= \text{Absorbed dose} (\eta\text{Gy}^{-1}) \times 1.2264 \times 10^{-3} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Cancer Risks Associated with Organs

This is about the chance of getting cancer for the duration of a lifetime for a certain level of exposure. It is expressed as a number that indicates the anticipated number of cancer cases in a given population following exposure to a carcinogen at a specific dose (Agbalagba, 2016). It's important to note that there is a direct correlation between elevated ELCR and an increased risk of blood, prostate, or breast cancer. Equation is used to calculate excess lifetime cancer risk (ELCR) and based on the calculated values of AEDE, the Excess Life Cancer Risk (ELCR) was calculated using the formula

$$\text{ELCR} (\text{mSv}^{-1}) = \text{AEDE} \times \text{Average Duration of Life (DL)} \times \text{Risk Factor (RF)} \quad (5)$$

Where DL is the average life expectancy (expected to be 70 years), AEDE stands for Annual Equivalent Dose Equivalent, and RF is the Risk Factor (Sv^{-1}), or the fatal cancer risk per Sievert. The public's RF value for stochastic impacts is set by ICRP at 0.05 (ICRP, 1993).

Organ Annual Effective Dosage

This is the radiation dose that each organ system in the body, including the whole body, kidney, testicles, ovaries, lung, and liver, has received. The organ dosages were not considered in many research articles. The quantity of natural background radiation received by each organ over the course of a year was determined by

computing the organ radiation doses owing to inhalation exposure channel manner using equation (6) and the annual effective data extracted. The formula given by Zaid et al., (2010) can be used to determine the effective dose rate given to a certain organ:

$$D_{organ} \text{ (mSvy-1)} = O \times AEDE \times F \quad (6)$$

where F is the conversion factor of the organ dose from inhalation, O is the occupancy factor (0.8), and AEDE is the annual effective dose. The conversion factors for the body's different organs are 0.68, 0.69, 0.62, 0.82, 0.58, 0.64, and

0.46 for the Whole Body, Bone Marrow, Kidney, Ovaries, Lung, and Liver, respectively.

The risk of organ cancer is often overlooked in the literature, while being a critical factor in assessing the potential health effects of ambient natural radiation in a given area. Individual organ cancer risk was determined using the organ dose previously computed.

Results

This section presents the findings from the measured BIR exposure levels and the estimated hazard indices for each of the six FCT area councils.

Table 1. The Average BIR Measurement from All the Area Councils of FCT

Area Council Code	Area Council Name	Lat.	Long.	BIR (μSv/hr)	BIR (mR/hr)
AMAC	Abuja Municipal Area Council	9.062°	7.422°	0.101	0.0101
KJ	Kuje	8.879°	7.228°	0.069	0.0069
BW	Bwari	9.282°	7.379°	0.115	0.0115
AB	Abaji	8.475°	6.945°	0.189	0.0189
KW	Kwali	8.840°	7.053°	0.126	0.0126
GW	Gwagwalada	8.955°	7.082°	0.130	0.013
Minimum				0.069	0.0069
Maximum				0.189	0.0189
Study Average				0.121	0.0121
World Average				0.2	0.013

Source: Authors Field survey, 2023

Figure 1. BIR Measurements of the Study Area
Source: Authors Field survey, 2023.

The BIR levels in the six area councils of the FCT that comprise the research areas as presented in Table 1 ranged from 0.0069mRh⁻¹ in Kuje area council to 0.0189mRh⁻¹ in Abaji area council, with a mean value of 0.0121mRh⁻¹, based on the results of the BIR level measurements. The average value found in the research areas is marginally below the 0.013mRh⁻¹

¹ global BIR level, indicating an almost high BIR level for the FCT. The BIR results is graphically represented in Figure 1.

Hazard Indices from all the Area Councils

This section presents the results of the hazard indices calculated in this study as presented in Table 2 and Figure 2.

Table 2. Hazard Indices from all LGAs of the State

Area Council Code	Area Council Name	Absorbed Dose Rate (nGy/hr)	Equivalent Dose (mSv/yr)	Annual Effective Dose Equivalent (O) (mSv/yr)	Excess Life Cancer Risk (μSv/yr)
AMAC	Abuja Municipal Area Council	87.87	0.849	0.11	0.39
KJ	Kuje	60.03	0.580	0.07	0.25
BW	Bwari	100.05	0.967	0.12	0.42
AB	Abaji	164.43	1.589	0.20	0.70
KW	Kwali	109.62	1.060	0.13	0.47
GW	Gwagwalada	113.10	1.093	0.14	0.49
Minimum		60.03	0.580	0.07	0.25
Maximum		164.43	1.589	0.20	0.70
Study Average		105.10	1.016	0.13	0.45

Source: Authors Field survey, 2023

Figure 2. Hazards Indices of Study Area

Source: Authors Field survey, 2023

Column 3 of Tables 2 displays the results of the gamma radiation absorbed dose rates for all the area councils of the study area. According to the results, the area councils' computed values are 87.87nGy/hr, 60.03nGy/hr, 100.05nGy/hr,

164.43nGy/hr, 109.62nGy/hr and 113.10nGy/hr, for AMAC, Kuje, Bwari, Abaji, Kawli and Gwagwalada, respectively, with a mean value of 105.85nGy/hr.

Column 4 of Table 2 displays the outcomes of the computed whole body equivalent dose rate. The computed values for AMAC, Kuje, Bwari, Abaji, Kwali and Gwagwalada are 0.849mSv^{-1} , 0.580mSv^{-1} , 0.967mSv^{-1} , 1.589mSv^{-1} , 1.060mSv^{-1} and 1.093mSv^{-1} , respectively, with a mean value of 1.023mSv^{-1} , based on the results.

With an overall mean annual equivalent dose rate of $0.13\text{mSv}/\text{yr}$, the computed annual effective dose equivalent values for the study area are presented in column 5 of Table 2 and include: $0.11\text{mSv}/\text{yr}$, $0.07\text{mSv}/\text{yr}$, $0.12\text{mSv}/\text{yr}$, $0.20\text{mSv}/\text{yr}$, $0.13\text{mSv}/\text{yr}$ and $0.14\text{mSv}/\text{yr}$ for AMAC, Kuje, Bwari, Abaji, Kwali and Gwagwalada, respectively.

For the research area, the estimated excess life cancer risks (ELCR) as calculated in column 6 of

Table 2 are $0.39\mu\text{Sv}/\text{yr}$, $0.25\mu\text{Sv}/\text{yr}$, $0.42\mu\text{Sv}/\text{yr}$, $0.70\mu\text{Sv}/\text{yr}$, $0.47\mu\text{Sv}/\text{yr}$ and $0.49\mu\text{Sv}/\text{yr}$, for AMAC, Kuje, Bwari, Abaji, Kwali and Gwagwalada, respectively, with an overall mean ELCR of $0.45\mu\text{Sv}/\text{yr}$.

Effective Dose Rate (D_{organ}) in mSv^{-1} to Different Body Organs or Tissues

The quantity of radiation that a person consumes and accumulates in their various body organs and tissues is estimated by the annual effective dose to organs model. After seven organs and tissues were analyzed, the results indicate (see Table 3) that the testes received the highest dose, with an average of 0.085mSv^{-1} , while the liver received the lowest dose, with an average of 0.047mSv^{-1} .

Table 3. Effective Dose Rate (D_{organ}) in mSv^{-1} to Different Body Organs or Tissues

Area Council Code	Area Council Name	Whole Body	Bone Marrow	Kidney	Testes	Ovaries	Lung	Liver
AMAC	Abuja Municipal Area Council	0.060	0.061	0.055	0.072	0.051	0.056	0.040
KJ	Kuje	0.038	0.039	0.035	0.050	0.032	0.036	0.026
BW	Bwari	0.065	0.066	0.060	0.079	0.056	0.061	0.044
AB	Abaji	0.109	0.110	0.100	0.131	0.092	0.102	0.074
KW	Kwali	0.071	0.072	0.064	0.085	0.060	0.067	0.048
GW	Gwagwalada	0.076	0.077	0.069	0.092	0.065	0.072	0.052
Minimum		0.038	0.039	0.035	0.050	0.032	0.036	0.026
Maximum		0.109	0.110	0.100	0.131	0.092	0.102	0.074
Study Average		0.070	0.071	0.064	0.085	0.060	0.065	0.047

Source: Authors Field survey, 2023

Figure 3. Effective Dose Rate (D_{organ}) to Different Body Organs or Tissues

Source: Authors Field survey, 2023

Discussion

The results presented showed that Abaji and Gwagwalada area councils have a relatively high BIR measurement. The reasons might be because of the urban mix character of Abaji and Gwagwalada area councils, where businesses and factories are sandwiched between residential areas, may be responsible for the relatively high mean values (i.e. 0.0189 and 0.013 mRh⁻¹, respectively) observed. The operating companies may be deploying materials that elevate the BIR exposure levels of the immediate environment. The geological and geographical settings of the sites, as well as the fertilizer and agrochemical applications within the homes and environmental farms, particularly in Abaji area council, may also be responsible for the high range readings. The Kuje area council's lowest BIR level of 0.0069mRh-1 can be ascribed to the council's utilization of low BIR contributing materials. The study's average BIR level is comparable to values reported in a few other regions of the world, including the Jhelum Valley in Pakistan Rafique et al., (2014); Turkey by Erees et al., (2006); and Japan by Chikasawa et al., (2001) as well as in Nigeria, including Avwiri et al., (2007) in the Ughelli region of Nigeria; Isa et al., (2021) in all local government areas of Kogi state; Akpabia et al., (2005) in Ikot Ekpene South-South Nigeria, Farai and Jibiri (2000) in Western Nigeria.

As for the hazard indices, the results obtained in this study in comparison to the values previously published by Rafique (2013), of 81.61 nGy/hr for Muzaffarabad and 102.70 nGy/hr for Poonch in Turkey (Rafique et al., 2013), as well as the Greek population with a value of 32 nGy/hr (Clouvas et al., 2004), the obtained mean gamma absorbed dose rates for the FCT (the study area) is significantly greater. Additionally, as the UNSCEAR (2000) report documents, the mean value obtained in this study surpass values recorded globally in certain regions or countries of the world (UNSCEAR, 2000). These countries or nations include Portugal (102nGy/hr), China (100nGy/hr), New Zealand (20nGy/hr), the United States

(38nGy/hr), the United Kingdom (60nGy/hr), Poland (67nGy/hr), Norway (80nGy/hr), and slightly above the value from Italy (105nGy/hr), among others (UNSCEAR, 2000). The gamma dose rates found in this study are comparable to the range of values reported in Turkey (Erees et al., 2007), Japan (Chikasawa et al., 2001), and Turkey (Amekudzie, 2011), which are 78.30–135.70nGy/hr, 13.8–187.0nGy/hr, and 75.0–509.38nGy/hr respectively. The mean value found in this study, however, is greater than the 59nGy/hr global population weighted average gamma dose rates estimate (UNSCEAR, 2000).

The equivalent dose rate computed for each of the six area councils shows that, while the values for the other area councils are marginally below the standard permissible limit of 1.0 mSvy⁻¹ for the public, the values for Abaji and Gwagwalada area councils are significantly above it (ICRP, 1990). The values obtained, however, are higher than those reported in several other nations worldwide (see Rafique et al., 2013; Clouvas et al., 2004; Erees et al., 2007; Chikasawa et al., (2001), which paint a picture of a radiologically contaminated environment. These results also are in consistent with other research conducted in Nigeria (see Avwiri et al., 2007; Akpabio et al., 2005; Agbalagba et al., 2009; Agbalagba and Meindinyo, 2010; Isa et al., 2021) among others.

The obtained annual effective dosage equivalent value is comparable to the levels reported in Saudi Arabia's Al-Rakkah (2015). The yearly effective dosage is 0.41 mSv/yr on average worldwide, of which 0.07 mSv/yr comes from outdoor exposure and 0.34 mSv/yr from interior exposure (Clouvas et al., 2004; Amekudzie, 2011; Al-Rakkah, 2015). The study's result is greater than the global average normal annual effective dosage level for outdoor environments, which is a sign of radioactive contamination and a potential source of FCT pollution.

The world average value of 0.29 x 10⁻³mSvy⁻¹ is greater than the average ELCR value found in the current study area (Taskin et al., 2009). The ELCR conclusion shows that there is no likelihood of cancer for study area residents who

will live in the city their entire lives due to BIR exposure.

These findings show that the estimated doses to the various organs under investigation are all less than the 1.0mSv yearly worldwide acceptable limit dose intake to the bodily organ. Food nutrient absorption rate provides justification for the comparatively higher dose to the testes and lower dose intake to the liver (Zaid et al., 2010; WHO, 1993). This demonstrates that the radiation dosage to these adult organs is not greatly affected by exposure to BIR levels in the FCT.

Conclusion

Since exposure to natural background radiation is an ongoing and inevitable aspect of human existence, the qualitative and quantitative assessment of exposure levels and doses within the environment is a crucial component of radiation protection. In order to review the background radiation levels in various locations of Nigeria quantitatively, the current work has been undertaken in this regard within the FCT. All the hazard indices including the excess life cancer risk, the mean absorbed dose rate and the annual effective dose equivalent rate levels are all above the standard permissible limits established by the International Commission on Radiological Protection (ICRP). As a result, the radiological assessment demonstrated that there is immediate radiological health effect on the general public as a result of background radiation exposure, there is a high chance that someone will get cancer over the course of a lifetime of exposure to the studied environments. In order to develop and monitor radiation protection measures as well as for future study, public health authorities and the government will use this work's conclusions as a baseline of critical importance.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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